

OPTIMISATION OF RECYCLING OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH A SUPERCRITICAL ACETONE/WATER SOLVENT

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ABSTRACT

The degradation of a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin using an acetone/water solvent mixture supplied in a ratio of 80:20 v/v has been investigated. Conditions ranging from 300 °C, 180 bar to 380 °C, 325 bar have been studied over a processing time of up to 2.5 h. At 300 and 310 °C, sufficient degradation was not observed, while above 340 °C, there was a loss in the weave architecture which would ultimately result in downgrading the material as an effective realignment process is yet to be developed. Therefore, optimum conditions of 320 °C, 195 bar have been identified as suitable for decomposing epoxy resins and recovering clean fibres. Here, a resin removal yield of more than 90 wt.% was achieved and the weave structure was retained. Quadratic trend lines were fitted to the degradation curves suggesting second order reaction kinetics. This was later verified through calculating effective rate coefficients for each temperature studied which were successfully used in an Arrhenius plot. From the data, the pre-exponential factor and activation energy for the process was found to be $61.0 \text{ g}_{\text{resin}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and 317 kJ.mol^{-1} respectively. In addition, preliminary analysis of the organic liquid fraction shows a complex mixture consisting of ketones, amines and cyclic compounds. If this mixture can be refined to a sufficient purity, it is possible these compounds can be used elsewhere in the chemical industry resulting in a significant environmental benefit.

1 INTRODUCTION

With global production capacity of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) expected to exceed 140,000 t by 2020 [1], there is a growing demand for more effective recycling techniques to be developed. The majority of CFRPs use a thermoset (e.g. epoxy) resin as the binding matrix due to good mechanical properties, resistance to change over a large temperature range and lower costs [2]. However, they are generally more difficult to recycle than thermoplastic based composites due to the cross-linked nature of the polymer chains. Pyrolysis is currently the only commercialised technique able to recover fibres suitable for reuse in the manufacture of new composite materials. As this process results in the loss of the resinous matrix, alternative methods capable of closing the loop of the supply chain have started to gain more interest.

Previous research has shown it is possible to recover clean fibres with similar properties to virgin material using various solvolytic techniques whereby the resin is dissolved in a suitable solvent. Under low temperature conditions (typically < 200 °C), it is necessary to use strong acids or oxidising agents which can lead to significant fibre damage and complex organic solutions. These are often difficult to separate in addition to being hazardous to human health, safety and the environment [3-9]. Although it is occasionally necessary to raise the temperature up to 450 °C, the use of generally recognised as safe (GRAS) solvents avoids the use of these harmful additives. Water, short-chain alcohols and acetone

have been considered and all are able to fully degrade thermoset resins without the need for a catalyst [10-17]. Organic compounds are generally able to recover clean fibres at lower temperatures than water, largely due to having a lower critical point. Propan-1-ol, for example, is able to recover clean fibres at 310 °C when operating semi-continuously [16] and similar results have been obtained with acetone at 320 °C [17]. Furthermore, it has been previously shown a combination of acetone and water mixed at a ratio of 80:20 v/v enhances the degradation of an epoxy resin [18]. This work aims to study the degradation reaction when using this solvent mixture in order to optimise process parameters such as reaction time and operating temperature in addition to calculating reaction kinetics.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The degradation reaction was studied using a composite material comprising of 20 plies of woven Toray T700 6k carbon fibre and an RTM6 epoxy resin. This is one of the most difficult polymers to degrade [19], therefore, if it is possible to recover fibres reinforcing this resin, it is highly likely the developed process will be suitable for recycling a wide range of CFRPs. The fibre volume content was 53 ± 1 % according to the manufacturer which corresponded to a resin content of 36 wt. %. This was confirmed with thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using an Exstar 6000 supplied by Seiko Instruments Inc. A sample size of $(10 \times 10 \times 6 \pm) \text{ mm}^3$ was used at a reactor loading of $30 \pm 1 \text{ mg}_{\text{resin}} \cdot \text{mg}_{\text{solvent}}^{-1}$.

To make the solvent mixture, analytic research (AR) grade acetone was supplied by Sigma Aldrich and combined with water from the mains supply in a ratio of 80:20 v/v.

2.2 Fibre Recovery

All experiments were completed with an electrically heated, 100 mL tubular batch reactor. Samples of the CFRP were placed into a stainless steel basket in order to avoid contact with the reactor walls; it is possible this would have caused some pyrolysis of the material. 50 mL of the solvent was added and the reactor heated to the desired temperature for various process times as specified in Table 1. This heating phase was 35 ± 5 minutes while the cooling phase, using forced air convection, lasted 25 minutes. Once cool, the fibres were removed and the organic liquid fraction recovered for analysis. Due to a light residue of the resin degradation products remaining on the fibre surface, it was necessary to wash the recovered fibres with acetone. All samples were dried overnight in a fume cupboard before characterisation.

Temperature (± 1 °C)	Induced Pressure (± 3 bar)	Reaction Times (min)
300	180	
310	187	0, 10, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90,
320	195	120, 150
340	235	
360	270	0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 60, 90,
380	325	150

Table 1: Reaction conditions investigated for the recovery of carbon fibre from RTM6 composite material

2.3 Fibre Characterisation

In order to quantify the mass of organics remaining, all recovered fibres were divided into 5 different aluminium crucibles and calcined in air at 500 °C. Each crucible was regularly removed,

cooled to room temperature and weighed. The process was repeated until the reduction in mass was negligible at which point it was assumed all resin or degradation products had been removed. Equations (1) and (2) were then used to calculate the mass of material remaining after each experiment and determine the resin removal yield (RRY). An average was calculated from the 5 samples used.

$$R_f \% = \frac{m_i - m_f}{m_i} \quad (1)$$

$$RRY \% = \frac{R_i - R_f}{R_i} \quad (2)$$

Where: R_f = Resin content after processing (%), m_i = Mass of sample after processing (g), m_f = Mass of sample after calcination (g), RRY = Resin removal yield (%) and R_i = Initial resin content (%).

2.4 Analysis of Degradation Products

The organic liquid fraction recovered after processing the samples was diluted by a factor of 1:30 v/v with the same acetone/water solvent mixture. Spectra of the compounds present were obtained with a Waters Corporation gas chromatography combined with time-of-flight mass spectrometry (GC-TOF MS). Products were identified with NIST MS Search 2.0 Library Software.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fibre Recovery

The effect of changing operating temperature and processing time on RRY is shown in Figures 1 and 2, below and it is apparent there is a strong linear dependence of temperature on RRY. At 300 and 310 °C, the RRY reaches a maximum of just 54 and 75 wt.% respectively after 2.5 hours of processing while complete degradation is observed in just 15 minutes at 360 °C. Extrapolating the data obtained for the 2 former temperatures show peaks in the RRY of 74 and 78 wt.% thereby suggesting that complete degradation is not possible at temperatures less than 320 °C. The residue remaining on the surface of the fibres is likely to hinder the adhesion of a new resin and increase the risk of fibre pull out. In addition, samples recovered after processing at 300 °C were still firmly bound together as shown by Figure 3a. However, with a 5% loss in the mass upon just reaching 300 °C, it is apparent the degradation reaction does start at a temperature lower than this. Upon raising the temperature to 320 °C, a peak RRY is observed at 90 wt.% after just 2 h of processing. Here, each ply of carbon fibre fabric is perfectly separated and the weave structure is maintained (see Figure 3b) suggesting the material is suitable for immediate reuse in the manufacture of a new composite material. Fibres recovered using this technique have also been used in the manufacture of a kayak [20].

Upon increasing the reactor temperature to 340 and 360 °C, the resinous matrix is completely decomposed in just 45 and 15 minutes respectively. Although experiments were carried out at 380 °C, the reaction proceeded so quickly, the resin was completely removed after just reaching the operating temperature. This is possibly due to surpassing the critical point of water meaning the entire solvent mixture is in the supercritical phase. As it has been previously suggested the preferred reaction mechanism is hydrolysis [18], the enhanced diffusivity and greater solvating power of supercritical water facilitates a significantly faster reaction rate. Despite the process requiring less than half the time, it is apparent there is significant damage to the fibres at 340 °C due to their “fluffy” quality as

Figure 1: Degradation rate of carbon fibre reinforced RTM6 epoxy resin at 300 to 360 °C after processing for between 0 and 2.5 h

Figure 2: Variation in degradation of carbon fibre reinforced RTM6 epoxy resin between 300 and 340 °C after processing for 30, 45 and 60 min

shown in Figure 3c. As an effective realignment technology is yet to be developed, this severely limits future applications, resulting in downgrading the material. However, previous research has

successfully recovered fibres retaining up to 98% of their original tensile strength under more extreme conditions [10, 12].

Figure 3: Samples of carbon fibre reinforced RTM6 epoxy resin after processing for a) 150 min at 300 °C; b) 120 min at 320 °C and c) 45 min at 340 °C

3.2 Reaction Kinetics

At 300 and 310 °C, the reaction proceeds almost linearly with time while between 320 and 340 °C, it is possible to fit a quadratic trend line to the data in Figure 1 suggesting second order reaction kinetics. Previous studies have also successfully modeled the degradation of epoxy resins as second order [10, 17]. This would suggest a two stage mechanism; mass transfer of the solvent molecule from the bulk fluid to the resin surface followed by the surface reaction. The thickness of the resin surrounding the fibre surface is small, therefore, it can be assumed reaction kinetics are proportional to the mass of resin remaining. This can be described by Equation 3.

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = -k_{eff} \times M^n \quad (3)$$

Separating the variables and integrating with boundary conditions at $t = 0$, $M = M_i$ and at $t = t$, $M = M$ gives Equation 4.

$$M = [M_i^{1-n} - (1-n) \times k_{eff} \cdot t]^{-\frac{1}{1-n}} \quad (4)$$

For a second order reaction, $n = 2$:

$$M = \frac{M_i}{1 + k_{eff} \cdot M_i \cdot t} \quad (5)$$

Rearranging for k_{eff} :

$$k_{eff} = \frac{M_i - M}{M_i \cdot M \cdot t} \quad (6)$$

Where M = mass of resin on fibre surface (g), t is reaction time (min), k_{eff} is the effective rate coefficient combining the influence of solvent mass transfer and reaction rate ($g^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) and n is the order of reaction.

Using the reaction data, it is therefore possible to draw an Arrhenius plot of $\ln(k_{eff})$ vs. $1/T$ as shown in Figure 4. As the Arrhenius equation (Equation 7) is in the form of $y = mx + c$, this gives a straight line. Extrapolating the data to the y-axis also allows the pre-exponential factor, k_0 , to be calculated while the gradient of the curve gives the activation energy (E_A). These have been found to be $61.0 \text{ g}_{resin}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and 317 kJ.mol^{-1} respectively.

$$\ln(k_{eff}) = \ln(k_0) - \frac{E_A}{R} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \quad (7)$$

With an R^2 value of 0.99, the data suggests the reaction does follow a second order mechanism and therefore the calculated values of k_0 and E_A have a good level of accuracy.

Figure 4: Arrhenius plot for the effective rate constant in the temperature range 300 to 360 °C.

3.3 Analysis of Degradation Products

Data for exact formulations of RTM6 epoxy resin is not readily available and is likely to vary depending on the manufacturer. However, common precursors include DGEBA and BADGE monomers while various amines are used as the cross-linking agents. Therefore, if an effective separation process can be developed, it is possible useful organic products can be recovered from the liquid fraction. However, it is first necessary to identify the compounds present. Figure 5 shows chromatograms for the organic liquid fraction recovered after processing the material for 2 h at 320 °C. Major peaks were defined as those with an intensity above 10% of the maximum observed. Using NIST library software, 6 major compounds were identified. 2 are ketones while 4 are cyclic molecules, 2 of which are amines. Although it is likely the epoxy resin used as part of this research differs from that examined in other works, similar compounds have previously been identified when studying the degradation products of thermoset resins [18]. If this mixture can be refined to a suitable purity, some compounds such as 2,5-diethyl-benzoamine (Figure 5a) could be used in the manufacture of a new resin thereby closing the loop of the supply chain. If this is not possible, alternative uses could involve further cracking molecules for use as nitrogen based fertilisers which still represents an improvement in resource efficiency compared to pyrolytic techniques.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Currently commercialised recycling techniques are only able to recover the fibres from CFRPs and as such, do not represent resource efficient processes. Solvolysis, however, has the potential to decompose the polymer matrix such that clean fibres and useful organic products are recovered. The research presented has identified optimum operating conditions for the degradation of an RTM 6 resin; after processing the samples for 2 h at 320 °C under batch conditions, plies of carbon fibre fabric were perfectly separated and suitable for immediate reuse. Below this point, it is doubtful complete degradation would be achieved with the acetone/water solvent mixture investigated while more extreme conditions resulted in the loss of the fibre structure. Through monitoring the degradation rate at different temperatures, it was also possible to study the reaction kinetics. It appears the decomposition is a second order process as a result of mass transfer of the solvent molecule and the

Figure 5: GC TOF-MS chromatograms identifying compounds present following the degradation of carbon fibre reinforced RTM6 after processing for 2 h at 320 °C.

degradation reaction at the surface of the resin. From the data, effective rate constants have been calculated and in turn, this allowed the pre-exponential factor and activation energy for the process to be found as $61.0 \text{ g}_{\text{resin}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $317 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Furthermore, 6 different compounds were identified as constituents of the organic liquid fraction. These are either cyclic aromatics, amines or ketones which, once separated, all have the potential to be used elsewhere in the chemical industry, if not as precursors to a new resin. This avoids the release of additional emissions to the atmosphere through pyrolysis and reduces the need to manufacture organic molecules from other sources such as crude oil resulting in a clear environmental benefit.

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